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DESIGNING MICRO AERIAL VEHICLES WITH INCREASED FLIGHT EFFICIENCY

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The spectrum of conflict in 21st Century war fighters has influenced and motivated this new development of micro aerial vehicles for surveillance. The prototype that we are proposing is a combination of MEMS and micro- electronic components with comparably - sized mechanical elements of varying complexity to achieve useful and unique functionality (e.g.:- integrated systems of sensors, actuators and processors). The complex design we developed was done by using CATIA and the prototype was done in rapid prototyping machine. Our basic design is to increase the efficiency of flight without increasing the wing span. We analyzed the flight in CFD.

Keywords: MEMS, Micro Aerial Vehicles, complex design.